

Unlocking liver physiology: comprehensive pathway maps for mechanistic understanding

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Abstract

In silico methods provide a resourceful toolbox for new approach methodologies (NAMs). They can revolutionize chemical safety assessment by offering more efficient and human-relevant alternatives to traditional animal testing. In this study, we introduce two Liver Physiological Maps (PMs); comprehensive and machine-readable graphical representations of the intricate mechanisms governing two major liver functions. These maps are designed to facilitate a deeper understanding of human liver function and its perturbations by chemicals. Built from manually curated literature, the Liver PMs standardize existing knowledge on liver lipid metabolism and bile acid biosynthesis and secretion. Available for online interactive visualization and exploration, these maps adhere to the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles, ensuring easy and open access, interoperability, and reusability. They offer a holistic view of liver-specific pathways, supporting the development of a more accurate and human-based strategy for next-generation risk assessment of chemicals.

Keywords:

physiological maps, toxicology, systems biology, hepatology, new approach methodologies.

49 1. Introduction

50 The liver is a vital organ responsible for several essential functions in the human body,
51 including metabolism, immunity, digestion, and detoxification of xenobiotics ([Chiang 2013](#);
52 [Boyer 2013](#); [Alves-Bezerra and Cohen 2017](#); [Verhoeven et al. 2024](#)). Its unique dual blood
53 supply from the portal vein and the hepatic artery allows it to interact with the endocrine and
54 gastrointestinal systems, supporting several metabolic functions such as lipid metabolism.
55 Additionally, the liver plays a crucial role in bile acid biosynthesis and secretion, which are vital
56 for preserving the body's homeostasis. Exposure to toxic substances can result in liver injury,
57 including cholestasis, steatosis, fibrosis, and cancer ([Gijbels and Vinken 2017](#); [Mellor,
58 Steinmetz, and Cronin 2016](#)). Therefore, comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms
59 that drive human liver functions is critical for advancing mechanistic-based risk assessment in
60 toxicology. This knowledge can pave the way for developing more precise and human-
61 centered approaches for identifying and evaluating chemical hazards and risks.

62 New approach methodologies (NAMs) for next generation risk assessment combine human-
63 oriented *in vitro* and *in silico* methods, including artificial intelligence (AI) tools and mechanistic
64 models, to unravel mechanisms of toxicity ([Vinken et al. 2021](#)). In this context, the
65 Physiological Maps (PMs) framework provides the blueprint for molecular mechanistic
66 understanding of toxicity processes, linking to specific disease mechanisms summarized into
67 qualitative and quantitative adverse outcome pathway (AOP) networks, and serving as a
68 biological foundation for the development of mode-of-action ontologies ([Desprez et al. 2019](#)).
69 PMs are standardized and machine-readable graphical representations of molecular and
70 cellular processes associated with specific cell and/or organ functions, including homeostatic
71 processes ([Staumont et al. 2024](#)). Their development process is highly inspired by the Disease
72 Maps (DMs) project ([Mazein et al. 2018](#); [Ostaszewski et al. 2019](#)). While DMs mostly focus on
73 representing disease mechanisms, PMs depict undisturbed physiology. They act as a
74 knowledge repository that integrates relationships curated from a range of sources, including
75 the literature and open access resources mapping pathways - such as Reactome ([Milacic et
76 al. 2024](#)), KEGG ([Kanehisa et al. 2023](#)), Wikipathways ([Agrawal et al. 2024](#)) and DMs modules
77 ([Fujita et al. 2014](#); [Ostaszewski et al. 2021](#); [Serhan et al. 2020](#)). Moreover, PMs are curated
78 for cell- and/or organ-specific scenarios. Like DMs, PMs are dynamic tools where new
79 knowledge is seamlessly integrated, resulting in the continuous generation of updated versions
80 through a community-based effort. They are machine-readable, as they rely on a standardized
81 Systems Biology Graphical Notation (SBGN) ([Novère et al. 2009](#)) and can therefore be stored
82 in different systems biology file formats (e.g., SBML, GPML - explained in **Box 1** - and others).
83 Additionally, they are designed in a modular, interoperable, and reusable manner, making
84 them adaptable for various cell-specific contexts, diseases, or physiological conditions and
85 perturbations.

86 In the present article, we present the development of two PMs of human liver functions: the
87 Liver Lipid Metabolism and the Liver Bile Secretion PMs (LiverLipidPM and LiverBilePM). We
88 also discuss their potential applications in toxicology and systems medicine.

90 2. Results and discussion

91 We developed two PMs, each covering an important liver function whose impairment can lead
92 to the distinct clinical conditions of steatosis and cholestasis. Both liver pathologies can be
93 caused by exogenous substances through various mechanisms.

94 The **LiverLipidPM** provides a detailed overview of the pathways involved in lipid metabolism
95 (**Figure 1**). More specifically, the biological processes involved in the synthesis of fatty acids,
96 triglycerides, and cholesterol, as well as their uptake and export mechanisms. In addition, the
97 map includes pathways related to lipid catabolism through mitochondrial and peroxisomal
98 activities. A dedicated submap illustrates specific mitochondrial functions, such as reactive
99 oxygen species scavenging and oxidative phosphorylation. The map also covers regulatory
100 mechanisms that maintain lipid homeostasis through hormone signaling, transcription factor
101 dynamics, and feedback loops. This PM depicts the complex network of biochemical reactions
102 and molecular interactions occurring within a generic hepatocyte, represented by a single
103 cellular compartment. To increase cell type specificity, the resource includes carefully curated
104 proteins, genes, and ribonucleic acid (RNA) molecules known to be expressed in liver cells,
105 validated against the Human Protein Atlas single cell datasets ([Karlsson et al. 2021](#)). This
106 curation process ensures that the visualization accurately reflects the unique molecular
107 landscape of hepatocytes, providing a comprehensive and tissue-specific representation of
108 cellular processes in the liver.

109 The **LiverBilePM** provides a detailed overview of the biological pathways involved in the
110 biosynthesis, transport, and secretion of bile acids in the liver and considers the interactive
111 interface between hepatocytes and cholangiocytes through the bile canaliculi (**Figure 2**). This
112 map also depicts cholesterol biosynthesis and metabolism, leading to bile acid biosynthesis
113 and their subsequent transport across cellular membranes into the canaliculi space. It also
114 includes pathways for lipoprotein uptake and efflux, as well as bile acid influx and recycling
115 mechanisms, including the cholehepatic shunt. Besides that, regulatory control mechanisms
116 through hormonal signaling, gene regulatory networks and adaptive tuning are also included.
117 Hepatocytes and cholangiocytes are represented as four main compartments, two for each
118 cell type, and a delimited space between two hepatocytes and two cholangiocytes represents
119 a bile duct and bile canaliculus, respectively. As with the LiverLipidPM, cellular specificity was
120 also taken into consideration, and map entities were curated using the Human Protein Atlas
121 resources for both cell types presented on the LiverBilePM.

122 Both maps integrate metabolism with signaling pathways and regulatory networks using a
123 systems biology approach, and they were constructed utilizing manually curated human-
124 relevant data. The PMs are designed to guide the development of mechanistic-based *in vitro*
125 test batteries, *in silico* methods including AI approaches, and mode-of-action ontologies, all
126 aimed at supporting the mechanistic prediction of chemical toxicities in humans ([Vinken et al.](#)
127 [2021](#); [Heusinkveld et al. 2021](#)).

128 Additionally, the liver PMs can be applied to visually overlay omics data onto the pathways
129 (**Figure 3B**) using, for example, the MINERVA (Molecular Interaction NEtwork VisuAlization)
130 platform ([Satagopam et al. 2016](#); [Hoksza et al. 2020](#)). This visualization resource allows for
131 the exploration of variability in cell physiology by comparing different conditions side-by-side.
132 For instance, **Figure 3B** illustrates five distinct clusters of hepatocytes from a Human Protein
133 Atlas single-cell dataset, overlaid on a section of the cholesterol biosynthesis pathway. By
134 leveraging the MINERVA platform features, it is possible to query external ontologies for
135 chemicals and drugs that interact with molecular targets present in the maps (**Figure 3C**). The
136 interactive version of both liver PMs can be accessed and explored on the following MINERVA
137 platform weblink: <https://ontox.elixir-luxembourg.org/minerva/>.

138 Additionally, PMs serve as repositories of existing biological knowledge, which can be used to
139 support the development of AOPs. Two recent efforts to map AOP networks for steatosis and

140 cholestasis highlight how toxicity mechanisms interact at a higher mechanistic level [\(Van](#)
141 [Ertvelde et al. 2023; Verhoeven et al. 2024\)](#). By providing a high-resolution molecular
142 description of these mechanisms, PMs are valuable for benchmarking AOP network coverage
143 of biological processes and identifying new molecular initiating event targets that lead to
144 pathway perturbations and downstream toxicological key events up to organ phenotypic
145 alterations. Moreover, they facilitate hypothesis generation for new AOPs, contributing to the
146 refinement, expansion, and validation of AOPs and AOP networks. Finally, they can also be
147 used as a basis for developing *in silico* models that address specific questions, as
148 demonstrated by the DMs community [\(Niarakis et al. 2024\)](#).

149 PMs are aligned with the FAIR principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and
150 Reusability [\(Wilkinson et al. 2016\)](#) and present a unique identifier upon storage in BioStudies
151 [\(Sarkans et al. 2018\)](#) for each released version
152 [\(<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/studies?query=ontox+physiological+map>\)](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/studies?query=ontox+physiological+map). They are open-
153 source, publicly accessible, and completely reusable, either in their entirety or as adaptable
154 modules. The MIRIAM (Minimal Information Requested In the Annotation of biochemical
155 Models) annotations [\(Juty, Le Novere, and Laibe 2012\)](#) enhance the link between PMs and
156 external databases for each node in the network. By incorporating annotated literature and
157 pathway resources into the edges of the map, it enhances confidence and traceability in the
158 information being presented. This ultimately increases the overall transparency of the data.
159 The accessibility and reusability of these PMs promote collaboration and knowledge sharing
160 within the scientific community, fostering advancements in curation efforts to expand these
161 resources.

162 **Challenges and Future Directions**

163 The Liver PMs, while extensive, do not capture all known molecular processes related to liver
164 functions. This limitation stems from the manual curation process, which, despite expert
165 involvement, is inherently constrained by time and resources. To enhance these maps, we
166 plan to explore AI-assisted systematic review methods [\(Verhoeven et al. 2024; Van Ertvelde](#)
167 [et al. 2023; Bozada et al. 2021\)](#) in the literature selection phase, and text mining and natural
168 language processing techniques in the curation phase [\(Corradi et al. 2022; Bachman, Gyori,](#)
169 [and Sorger 2023\)](#). While AI-driven data extraction from text still faces challenges, such as
170 avoiding AI-generated hallucinations, this level of automation can complement manual
171 validation efforts.

172 By utilizing large-scale data analysis and machine learning techniques, we can discover novel
173 molecular relationships and expand the resource's detail and coverage, with the goal of more
174 accurately describing human physiology. Examining differentially expressed genes across
175 variations in standard physiological conditions (e.g., gender, age, populations, genotypic
176 variations) can help to illuminate the mechanistic differences leading to diverse outcomes upon
177 therapy administration or chemical exposure. Additionally, data-driven approaches for
178 reconstructing mechanistic pathways [\(Miagoux et al. 2021\)](#) can help to address gaps in our
179 understanding of human physiology.

180 To support research into chemical-induced toxicity endpoints, both PMs were specifically
181 developed as tools fit for this purpose. However, the fact that they are modular and
182 interoperable makes them valuable assets for the broader hepatology community, extending
183 their usefulness beyond the scope of toxicology.

184

185 3. Conclusion

186 The Liver PMs were primarily designed to serve as a valuable resource for toxicology research.
187 They were built to guide the refinement of AOP networks, enhance our understanding of
188 human physiological mechanisms, and support the establishment of human-oriented *in silico*
189 and *in vitro* test batteries for chemical toxicity assessment. Additionally, these maps were also
190 intended to provide a rationale for creating dynamic computational models and to lay the
191 groundwork for mode-of-action ontologies and mechanistic AI tools in toxicology. Beyond their
192 initial focus, the Liver PMs may also be applicable to systems biology and drug discovery. As
193 research progresses, these maps could become valuable in various aspects of pharmaceutical
194 development, including drug repurposing efforts.

195

196 4. Methods

197 The establishment of the PMs involves several steps: literature selection and curation,
198 overview model representation, pathway resource screening, extraction of molecular
199 relationships, nomenclature standardization, cell type curation, network diagramming, and
200 expert review. **Figure 4** highlights the entire workflow, detailing the key resources used in each
201 phase.

202 Data curation

203 To build the PMs, domain experts reviewed relevant literature, encompassing review papers
204 and book chapters. Mechanisms identified in the selected literature were compiled into a list,
205 and key terms from this list were incorporated into an overview model. Pathways from
206 established resources such as Reactome ([Gillespie et al. 2022](#)), KEGG ([Kanehisa et al. 2023](#)),
207 Wikipathways ([Martens et al. 2021](#)) and DMs reusable modules ([Fujita et al. 2014](#);
208 [Ostaszewski et al. 2021](#); [Serhan et al. 2020](#)) were screened for relevance, and pertinent
209 models were extracted for further refinement and inclusion in the PMs. These sources served
210 as the foundation for constructing the molecular diagrams. The process involved identifying
211 molecular interactions within normal physiological processes, followed by extracting and
212 detailing the causal relationships among them. Vocabulary was standardized using symbols
213 approved by the HUGO (Human Genome Organization) Gene Nomenclature Committee
214 (HGNC) ([Seal et al. 2023](#)) for genes, RNAs, and proteins, and Gene Ontology ([The Gene
215 Ontology Consortium et al. 2023](#)) Biological Function terms for phenotypes where relevant.
216 Cell-type-specific isoforms of proteins were verified against the Human Protein Atlas -
217 [proteinatlas.org](#) ([Karlsson et al. 2021](#)) to curate pathways relevant to a specific cell-type.

218 Graphical representation

219 The SBGN ([Novère et al. 2009](#)) Process Description (PD) language ([Rouhny et al. 2019](#)) was
220 the first choice of standard for pathway representation due to its ability to provide a high level
221 of granularity, mechanistic insights, and a clear sequence of events. In instances where
222 available information was sparse or insufficiently detailed for a full PD representation, a
223 pragmatic approach was adopted. This consisted of combining SBGN Activity Flow ([Mi et al.
224 2015](#)) modules into the PD representation. This allowed for maintaining a balance between
225 human readability and the need for flexibility when applying different analysis pipelines.

226 Diagram editor and visualization platform

227 The maps were created and edited using the CellDesigner pathway editor ([Funahashi et al.](#)
228 [2008](#)). For the domain expert review phase, the MINERVA platform ([Gawron et al. 2016](#);
229 [Hoksza et al. 2020](#)) was employed. MINERVA's well-structured commenting system, along
230 with its map visualization and exploration capacities powered by the Google Maps API,
231 facilitated the review process.

232 Documentation

233 To harness the full potential of PMs, a collaborative effort between domain experts and the
234 curation team was undertaken to annotate and document the maps. This process involved the
235 development of curation guidelines ([Ladeira et al. 2024](#)), coupled with comprehensive planning
236 documents, as well as detailed tables of contents ([https://github.com/ontox-](https://github.com/ontox-maps/guides_and_documentation)
237 [maps/guides_and_documentation](https://github.com/ontox-maps/guides_and_documentation)). We followed a comprehensive guide from the DMs
238 community ([Mazein et al. 2023](#)), reinforcing adherence to the FAIR principles ([Wilkinson et al.](#)
239 [2016](#)). Metadata, including literature references, pathway resource references, and identifiers,
240 can be found annotated directly into the SBML files of the maps. This approach not only
241 facilitates the use of PMs within the toxicology ecosystem but also ensures that other
242 researchers can seamlessly integrate and utilize these resources.

243

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251

252 Declaration of competing interests

253 The authors declare they have no competing interests.

254

255 Consent for publication

256 All authors agree to the publication of this study.

257

258 CRediT author statement

259 **Luiz Ladeira:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original
260 Draft, Visualization, Writing - Review & Editing. **Anouk Verhoeven:** Investigation, Data
261 Curation, Visualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing. **Jonas van**
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263 Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Alessio Gamba:** Methodology, Data

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266 **Heusinkveld**: Methodology, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Ramiro Jover**:
267 Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Mathieu Vinken**: Conceptualization,
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279

280 Data availability

281 The dataset is available in the BioStudies database (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies>) under
282 accession numbers S-ONTX35 (LiverBilePM) & S-ONTX36 (LiverLipidPM). All the maps are
283 available at our GitHub organization (<https://github.com/ontox-maps>) and at the ONTOX
284 MINERVA platform (<https://ontox.elixir-luxembourg.org/minerva/>), under the license Creative
285 Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) License
286 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

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Resource	Definition/comment
New Approach Methodologies (NAMs)	New approach methodologies (NAMs), are non-animal testing methods designed to reduce and replace existing traditional animal-based testing systems. Resource: https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/testing/new-approach-methodologies-in-toxicology.htm
Disease Maps	Disease Maps are visual representations of disease mechanisms in a human- and machine-readable way. Each project in the Disease Maps community integrates molecular interactions and pathways involved in a particular pathological scenario. More recently, physiological maps and adverse outcome pathways have also been integrated into the Disease Maps project portfolio. Resource: https://disease-maps.org/
Systems Biology Graphical Notation (SBGN)	Systems Biology Graphical Notation: a standardized graphical representation of biological mechanisms. SBGN is composed of three different types of representations: Activity Flow, Process Description and Entity Relationships. Resource: https://sbgn.github.io/
SBGN Process Description	A type of SBGN representation in which a network is directed, sequential, and mechanistic. It allows an understanding of the temporal aspect of biochemical interactions. Resource: https://sbgn.github.io/specifications
SBGN Activity Flow	A type of SBGN representation in which a network is directed and sequential but not mechanistic at the molecular level. It shows the flow of information between biochemical entities, omitting information about how interactions occur, and is particularly convenient for representing the effects of perturbations. Resource: https://sbgn.github.io/specifications
HGNC approved symbol	HUGO (Human Genome Organization) Gene Nomenclature Committee: official gene names assigned by experts. Used for consistent gene identification. Resource: https://www.genenames.org/
Gene Ontology (GO) Biological Function	Gene Ontology Biological Function: standardized terms describing gene roles in organisms. Part of a larger system for classifying gene functions. Resource: http://geneontology.org/
Reactome	Reactome is a large database of expert-curated biological pathways and reactions. Provides visualization and analysis tools for these processes. Resource: https://reactome.org/
WikiPathways	WikiPathways is a community-curated biological pathway database. Allows researchers to contribute and edit pathway information. Resource: https://www.wikipathways.org/
Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG)	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes is a database of genetic and molecular information, including pathway resources. Focuses on the systemic functions of genes and molecules. Resource: https://www.genome.jp/kegg/
Systems Biology Markup Language (SBML)	Systems Biology Markup Language: standard format for representing biological models in a machine-readable manner. Facilitates the exchange of models between different software tools. Resource: http://sbml.org/
Graphical Pathway Markup Language (GPML)	Graphical Pathway Markup Language: the WikiPathways standard format for representing biological models in a machine-readable manner. Facilitates the exchange of models between different software tools. Resource: https://pathvisio.org/documentation/GPML2021-doc.html

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473 **Figure 1.** The Liver Lipid Metabolism Physiological Map (LiverLipidPM) is focused on lipid
 474 metabolism, including transport across hepatocyte membranes, lipid and cholesterol
 475 biosynthesis, and fatty acid oxidation. The overview model includes a conceptual illustration of
 476 these processes in the hepatocyte, serving as a mini-map to the molecular map. In the figure,
 477 we linked the pathways and mechanisms listed in the pathway highlights to the respective
 478 regions in which they are represented in the detailed molecular map.

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483 **Figure 2.** The Liver Bile Acids Secretion Physiological Map (LiverBileAcidsPM) focuses on bile
 484 acid biosynthesis in hepatocytes, transport across hepatocyte and cholangiocyte membranes,
 485 cholehepatic shunt, cell junction dynamics, and recycling processes. The overview model
 486 includes a conceptual illustration of these processes in the hepatocyte, serving as a mini-map
 487 to the molecular map. In the figure, we linked the pathways and mechanisms listed in the
 488 pathway highlights to the respective regions in which they are represented in the detailed
 489 molecular map.

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513 **Figure 3.** MINERVA platform visualization of a physiological map. The **upper panel** displays
 514 a full map visualization in the MINERVA platform interface. A zoom on a pathway (cholesterol
 515 biosynthesis) is depicted in **(A)**, showing the graphical representation of the molecular
 516 interactions using the Systems Biology Graphical Notation. Panel **(B)** shows how data can be
 517 visualized: a color gradient is used to represent a range of numerical values associated with
 518 each map entity. In this particular example, the intensity of the blue color indicates the level of
 519 RNA amounts in hepatocytes (darker shades represent higher levels) from different single-cell
 520 data clusters using a dataset from the Human Protein Atlas ([proteinatlas.org](https://www.proteinatlas.org)) ([Karlsson et al. 2021](#)).
 521 And panel **(C)** shows the output of a drug query for a specific protein target (HMGCR),
 522 which retrieves results from DrugBank ([Knox et al. 2024](#)) and ChEMBL ([Zdrazil et al. 2024](#)).

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535 **Figure 4.** Physiological Maps curation workflow, from literature curation to expert review.
 536 KEGG stands for Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes; PMID for PubMed Identifier;
 537 HGNC for HUGO (Human Genome Organization) Gene Nomenclature Committee; SBML for
 538 Systems Biology Graphical Notation; and MINERVA for Molecular Interaction NETwork
 539 VisuAlization.

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